

REPORT:

A5.1.7: Report on reasons for failure of microfluidic devices

Work package 5

<https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written as part of activity A5.1.7 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

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The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

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1. Scope

This document provides the investigation on why microfluidic devices fail.

Activity No. (where applicable)	5.1.7
Brief Activity Description	A report highlighting how and why microfluidic devices fail will be produced including a checklist that can be used by the full microfluidic supply chain. This report/paper will be made available on the project website and distributed to the microfluidic community and other potential end users by email.
Action by whom	Hahn-Schickard (Lead), all partners
Due by	M36

2. Links to other relevant reports

- A1.2.3 Documented example of the test protocol for leakage and burst pressure. [Link](#)
- A3.2.7 Documented example of surface roughness measurements. [Link](#)
- A2.2.2 Development of test protocols for microfluidic devices. [Link](#)
- A2.3.2 Test protocols for liquid properties related to microfluidic devices. [Link](#)
- A2.1.1 Metrology Methodology. [Link](#)

3. Sources of information

In general people only publish their successes, not their failures. Hence, it is not easy to find relevant publications on failure modes in microfluidic devices or components. However, we do have an idea of what kind of major failures the microfluidic community encounters, thanks to contacts with the relevant actors in this field. This report provides an assortment of failure modes that the MFMET team members are looking at. The main results are presented below.

4. Results of microfluidic surveys: reliability of microfluidics-based devices and components

A microfluidic device/system is generally defined as a component that handles a small volume (micro- or nanoliter) of liquids or gases by, for example, transporting, mixing, dividing or analysing them. Applications include biomedical and chemical analysis technologies, among others. One of the goals in the development of microfluidic systems is to offer miniaturized and compact overall solutions from sample input, sample preparation, up to the display of analysis results. Therefore, such systems are also referred to as Lab-on-Chip (LOC), Organ-on-a-chip (OoC) or Micro Total Analysis System (μ TAS). Miniaturization offers numerous advantages such as lower sample/reagent consumption, reduced risk of contamination, lower cost and time per analysis, reduction of tedious laborious steps, improved sensitivity and specificity, and increased reliability, to name a few.

4.1. Conclusions of a survey from 2015

In the first half of 2015, a survey was held among microfluidic experts. 155 participants filled in the survey. The major conclusions regarding reliability were:

Three types of components are seen as major sources of reliability problems:

- **Pumps / flow control devices** or elements
 - Flow control issues (**bubble formation, flow / pressure changes and clogging**) are on top of the list of failure modes. For discontinuous flow the major problems are also flow-related, with e.g. droplet size variation due to flow control instabilities far on top.
- **Microfluidic interconnections mainly causing leakage**
- **Filters**

It is not surprising that problems increase when components are reused. For example, **cross-contamination** and **material-related reasons** like **coating failure** and **degassing, adsorption, absorption** are commonly seen. It is interesting to note that there is an increase in flow-related problems when reusing components.

Two out of the three of the most often mentioned problems when it comes to **electrical parts** are fabrication related, specifically **faulty connections** and **parasitic capacitance**. For **optical biosensors** the main problems are **unspecific adsorption** and **material autofluorescence**.

For those that are using disposables, the sensors are often the cause of reliability problems, but also flow control related parts and devices. As many of the reusable devices are used for processing, sensors do not cause many problems, but flow control and microfluidic interconnections do.

There seems to be a relation between the issues “**bubble formation**”, “**dead volume**” and “**degassing, adsorption and absorption**”.

4.2. Conclusions from interviews made to Industry between 2021 and 2022

During the months of November 2021 - January 2022 industry experts from 10 organisations (of which 9 industrial, 2 USA-based, 8 Europe-based) were interviewed about their measurement priorities with regards to manufacturing of microfluidic devices.

Measurement priorities for suppliers of microfluidic components and devices during fabrication based on industry experts are:

1. Measurement that affects pressure decay and flow resistivity in the device (e.g. wettability, deviation from the nominal dimensions).
2. Measurement that affects bonding quality of polymer devices (e.g. glass transition temperature, melting temperature, molecular weight number and distribution)
3. Leakage test / burst pressure test / maximum operational pressure test.
4. Agreement about quality information of incoming materials like: optical transmission / auto fluorescence of involved materials, thickness of glass substrates.

Other topics of interest:

- Measurement of fast changing flow-rates.
- Bio-viability check after deposition/coating/dipping on the chip / in the device.

4.3. Relevant conclusions from a Workshop on Standardization held in Lyon in 2023

Lastly, we held a workshop “On the road to standardization in microfluidics and organ-on-chip”, where we identified several challenges for the microfluidic community.

From the workshop we identified challenges and focal points for metrology:

- Liquid properties
- Problems associated with the measurement inside channels (e.g. dimensions, roughness)
- Characterization of passive systems, what to report as a supplier and how to measure / qualify microfluidic devices / systems?
- Detection / sensors: calibration of sensors at sensor level or system level?
- Reliability
 - Leakage
 - Relation between air leakage, liquid leakage and contamination leakage
 - Bubble presence
 - Dead volume
 - Clogging
 - Contamination
 - Bonding strength

Apart from metrology, the 2023 workshop in Lyon discussed topics related to standardisation:

- Connector reliability
- Modularity and assembly
- Interfaces that allow interchangeability of equipment

4.4. Conclusions: Why and how microfluidic devices and components fail

In conclusion, the failure of microfluidic devices is often multifactorial, involving issues related to flow control, component reuse, fabrication, sensors, interconnections, and measurement priorities. Addressing these issues is crucial for improving the reliability and performance of microfluidic devices.

1. **Flow Control Issues:** Problems with pumps, flow control devices, and filters are common. These issues often manifest as bubble formation, flow/pressure changes, and clogging. These problems are exacerbated in discontinuous flow systems, where droplet size variation due to flow control instabilities is a major concern. Also, the use of non-calibrated and non-traceable instruments can cause problems related to the performance of the entire microfluidic system due to large flow rate errors.
2. **Component Reuse:** Reusing components increases the likelihood of problems. Cross-contamination is a primary concern, but material-related issues like coating failure, degassing, adsorption, and absorption also occur. Interestingly, flow-related problems also increase when reusing components.
3. **Fabrication Issues:** In terms of electrical parts, faulty connections and parasitic capacitance, which are fabrication-related, are often mentioned. For optical biosensors, unspecific absorption is a significant problem.
4. **Sensors and Interconnections:** For disposable devices, sensors and flow control related parts and devices often cause reliability problems. In reusable devices used for processing, sensors do not cause many problems, but flow control and microfluidic interconnections do. It is essential to comprehend and take care of the key parameters that control the operation and performance of microfluidic devices, such as connecting components, as they are crucial links between the microworld and the macroworld. To successfully integrate the parameters that affect the performance of the microfluidic systems, the following criteria should be considered among others: ease of handling, overall compatibility of materials, adequate dimensions, and no leakage.
5. **Measurement Properties:** Anything that affects pressure decay and flow resistivity in the device, bonding quality of polymer devices, leakage test/burst pressure test/maximum

operational pressure test, and quality information of incoming materials are all crucial measurement properties during fabrication.

6. **Challenges:** measurement of liquid properties and their influence, problems associated with measurement inside channels, characterization of passive systems, detection/sensors, and reliability issues like leakage, bubble presence, dead volume, clogging, contamination, and bonding strength.

5. Failure mechanisms and strategies to avoid them

A microfluidic device/system often consists of two components such as a microfluidic chip and a device for processing this chip, which may include, for example, a drive unit or an analysis unit.

If we now look at the error mechanisms of the systems, we can distinguish between **errors in the production** of these systems, which lead to a certain amount of rejects, or **errors in the operation/handling** of these systems. Both types of error are examined in more detail in the next two sections.

5.1. Production-related failures of microfluidic devices

- **Fabrication Errors:** These include issues like faulty connections, wrong dimensions, parasitic capacitance, and unspecific absorption in optical biosensors. These are often due to errors in the manufacturing process.
 - **Possible solutions:**
 - Improved Fabrication Techniques: Ensuring precise fabrication can help prevent issues like faulty connections and unspecific absorption in optical biosensors. This includes the use of high-quality materials and advanced manufacturing processes.
 - Use quality assurance and traceable measures and monitoring during production.
- **Material Quality:** The quality of incoming materials like optical transmission/auto fluorescence of polymer materials, thickness of glass substrates, etc., can affect the overall quality of the microfluidic device. Poor quality materials can lead to device failure.
- **Bonding Quality:** Anything that affects the bonding quality of polymer, metal, ceramics, glass, etc., devices can lead to failure. This includes factors like glass transition temperature, melting temperature, molecular weight number, and distribution. Surface roughness may also affect the bonding quality, where smoother surfaces are typically bonded more successfully especially for thermoplastic or glass chips.

5.2. Operational/Handling Failures of microfluidic devices

- **Flow Control Issues:** Problems with pumps, flow control devices, flexible membranes and filters are common. These issues often manifest as bubble formation, flow/pressure changes, and clogging or the membrane tends to stick to the cavities.
 - a. Regular maintenance and calibration of pumps or any flow generator can prevent flow control issues.
 - b. Bubble formation in the channel can be prevented/minimized by the following measures:
 - i. Degassing the medium
 - ii. Using bubble traps
 - iii. Adopting cleaning procedures like flushing (e.g. with an alcohol, iso-propanol)
 - iv. Prevent temperature variation in the system

- c. Clogging can be prevented/minimized by the following measures:
 - i. Using filters to minimize particles in your test fluid
 - ii. Cleaning procedures like flushing (e.g. with an alcohol, iso-propanol)
 - iii. Prevent temperature variation in the system
 - d. Clogging or malfunctioning of the chip can cause damage on flow meters if they are placed between the flow generator and the chip. With this positioning, clogging can cause pressure to become too high, potentially leading to damage or breakage of the flow meter. High pressure that exceeds the flow meter's maximum pressure rating can cause it to malfunction or break.
 - i. Possible solution: To prevent this issue, it is recommended to place the flow meter downstream from the chip. This positioning ensures that the chip bears the brunt of the pressure from the flow generator, reducing the pressure experienced by the flow meter. As a result, the flow meter is less likely to be damaged by high pressure. However, it's important to ensure that the chip can withstand the pressure from the flow generator. Regular maintenance and checks can help prevent damage to both the chip and the flow meter. The exact positioning can depend on the specific setup and requirements of the microfluidic system. Always refer to the manufacturer's instructions or consult with a microfluidics expert when setting up the system.
- **Component Reuse:** Reusing components increases the likelihood of problems. Cross-contamination is a primary concern, but material-related issues like coating failure, degassing, adsorption, and absorption also occur.
 - Possible solution: Careful reuse of components. Implementing protocols for the safe reuse of components can help prevent cross-contamination and material-related issues like coating failure, degassing, adsorption, and absorption.
 - **Sensor and Interconnection Failures:** For disposable devices, sensors and flow control related parts and devices often cause reliability problems. In reusable devices used for processing, sensors do not cause many problems, but flow control and microfluidic interconnections do.
 - a. Interconnection problems (like connectors that are not tight and can cause leakage in the system) can be prevented/minimized using the following measures:
 - i. Use recommended and tight connectors.
 - ii. Use Teflon tape for sealing.
 - iii. Replace hoses and connectors with new ones of the same type, or other try other materials/brands.

6. References

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